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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLETS CONTAINING ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY – METFORMIN HCl

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ABSTRACT

Mucoadhesive tablets is the preferable route of drug delivery due to the ease of administration, patient compliance, and flexibility in formulation. Every patient would always like to have an ideal drug delivery system possessing the two main properties that are a single dose or less frequent dosing for the whole duration of treatment and the dosage form must release the active drug directly at the site of action. The most frequent polymers used are those derived from HPMC 15M, HPMC 100M and HPMC 4M. The results of Swelling index, mucoadhesive strength and *in vitro* disintegrating time (sec) ranged from 103.12 to 93.31, 12.11 to 18.16 and 5.02 to 6.15 min respectively. The *In vitro* dissolution profile indicated faster and maximum drug release from the formulation F4. For the F4 formulation diffusion exponent n value is in between 0.45 to 0.89 so they are following non fickian anomalous diffusion model. Among other results, this article demonstrates that this technology depends on a detailed analysis between the polymer, the physical characteristics of the tablet, the physicochemical characteristics of the drug to be incorporated and the buccal region in which it will remain in contact.

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INTRODUCTION

Oral delivery is by far the preferable route of drug delivery due to the ease of administration, patient compliance, and flexibility in formulation. Adhesion can be defined as the bond produced by contact between a pressure sensitive adhesive and a surface. The American Society of Testing and Materials has defined it as the state in which two surfaces are held together by interfacial forces, which may consist of valence forces, interlocking action or both. Mucoadhesive drug delivery systems prolong the residence time of the dosage form at the site of application or absorption. They facilitate an intimate contact of the dosage form with the underlying absorption surface and thus improve the therapeutic performance of the drug. Mucoadhesion can be characterized as the state in which two materials adhere to each other for extended periods of time with the help of interfacial forces and when one of these materials is biological in nature, the phenomenon is known as mucoadhesion [1-3]. However, the main component responsible for its viscoelastic properties is the glycoprotein mucin as shown in Fig No: 1. The term mucoadhesion is the “attachment of an engineered or natural macromolecule to mucus and additionally epithelial surface”.

Figure No 1: Viscoelastic properties is the glycoprotein mucin.

Introduction of sustained release (SR) has given a new breakthrough for novel drug delivery system (NDDS) in the field of Pharmaceutical technology. It excludes complex production procedures such as coating and palletization during manufacturing and drug release rate from the dosage form is controlled mainly by the type and proportion of polymer used in the preparations. SR system generally doesn't attain zero order type release and usually try to mimic zero order release by providing the drug in a slow first order [4-6]. Designing sustained-release drug delivery system in most of the orally administered drugs, targeting is not a primary concern and it is usually intended for drugs to penetrate to the general circulation and perfuse to other body tissues. For this reason, most systems employed are of the sustained release variety. It is assumed that increasing concentration at the epithelial membrane to the blood [7-10]. There are a variety of both physicochemical and biological factors that come into play in the design of such system.

Diabetes mellitus type II is a chronic, progressive disease that has no established cure, but does have well-established treatment which can delay and sometimes avoid most of the formerly inevitable consequences of the condition. There are two main goals of treatment [11-15].

1. Reduction of mortality and concomitant morbidity
2. Preservation of quality of life

Metformin HCL (MH; mol. formula $C_4H_{11}N_5$) is a widely used biguanide anti-diabetic drug for the management of diabetes mellitus.¹⁰ This is the first-line drug of choice for type-II diabetes.⁹ Metformin is also an “insulin sensitizer,” meaning that it works to make the cells in your body more receptive to insulin. When cells are insulin sensitive, they are able to take more glucose from the blood to be used for energy [16-19]. Because metformin does not signal the pancreas to release insulin, there is little risk of low blood sugar (hypoglycemia) when taking this drug.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The drug Metformin.HCl was gifted from Mumak labs, Mumbai and Mucoadhesive polymers HPMC K 100M, HPMC K 4M, HPMC K 15M, sodium CMC were obtained from SR Scientifics.

METHODS:

PREFORMULATION STUDIES:

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The physical properties of the physical mixture were compared with those of plain drug. Samples were mixed thoroughly with 100 mg potassium bromide IR powder and compacted under vacuum at a pressure of about 12 psi for 3 minutes. The resultant disc was mounted in a suitable holder in Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 3,500 cm to 500 cm. the resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum changes [20-22].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC).

DSC can be used to determine the compatibility between the drug and excipients and also used to evaluate the crystalline state of the drug. Thermal characteristics of the same materials that examined in FTIR study were determined by an automatic thermal analyzer system (Shimadzu, DSC- 60, Japan). Accurately weighed samples (5mg) were placed in non-hermetically aluminum pans and heated at the rate of 10 °C/minute against an empty aluminum pan as a reference covering a temperature range of 40 °C to 300 °C [23-24].

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLETS

Table No: 1 Design and Development of Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablets.

Materials (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Metformin	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500
HPMC15M	15	20	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMC100M	-	-	-	15	20	25	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMC4M	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	20	25	-	-	-
Na.CMC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	20	25
MCC	80	75	70	80	75	70	80	75	70	80	75	70
Ethyl cellulose	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Mg.stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Lactose	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
Talc	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

Before going to direct compression all the ingredients were screened through sieve no. 100 except lubricant (mg. stearate). All the ingredients were thoroughly blended in the glass mortar with pestle for 15 mins. After sufficient mixing, lubricant was added and again mixed for additional 2-3 mins. Before compression, hardness was adjusted and compressed into 500 mg each tablet using tablet compression machine equipped with 250 mm flat faced, bevel edge punches on 12th station rotary tablet machine and same hardness was used for the required number of the table[25-29].

PRECOMPRESSION STUDIES OF METFORMIN MUCOADHESIVE GRANULES:

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per pharmacopeia[30-35].

Angle of Repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane[36-38].

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

h= height of the pile

r = radius of the pile

Bulk Density

Bulk density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together[39-42].

$$\text{Bulk density} = M/V_0$$

Where, M =Weight of sample

V₀ = apparent volume of the powder

Tapped Density:

After carrying out of the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until the difference between succeeding measurement is less than 2%.

$$T=M/V$$

Where T = tapped density

M= weight of sample

V= tapped volume of powder

Carr's Index:

Carr's index is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities [43-46].

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(t - b) / t] \times 100$$

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLET OF METFORMIN HCL.

Metformin HCl tablets were prepared by direct compression method 500mg tablets were prepared using HPMC 15M, HPMC 100M, HPMC 4M and sodium CMC as a diluent, binder, lubricant and disintegrants at different concentration were passed in #40. All the above ingredients were properly mixed together in a poly bag. Talc and magnesium were passed through sieve #80 and blended with the initial mixture in a poly bag. The powder blend was compressed into tablets on a ten-station rotary punch – tableting machine (Reek Mini Press -1) using 7mm concave punch set [47-52].

POST FORMULATION STUDIES OF METFORMIN MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS:**Hardness test:**

Tablets require a certain amount of strength, or hardness and resistance to friability, to withstand mechanical shocks of handling in manufacture, packaging, and shipping. The hardness of the tablets was determined using Monsanto Hardness tester. It is expressed in Kg/cm²[53].

Friability test:

It is the phenomenon whereby tablet surfaces are damaged and/or show evidence of lamination or breakage when subjected to mechanical shock or attrition. The friability of tablets was determined by using Electro lab, USP EF 2 friabilator. It is expressed in percentage (%) [54].

$$F = \frac{W_{\text{initial}} - W_{\text{final}}}{W_{\text{initial}}} \times 100$$

Weight variation test:

The tablets were selected randomly from each formulation and weighed individually to check for weight variation

Drug content uniformity:

Four tablets weighed and crushed in a mortar then weighed powder contain equivalent to 10 mg of drug was taken and dissolved in 100 ml methanol, from this solution 1 ml of solution was diluted to 10 ml of methanol again 1 ml solution from this diluted up to 10 ml with methanol and assayed for drug content at 237.5 nm [55].

In vitro dissolution studies of Mucoadhesive buccal tablet:

Dissolution rate was studied by using basket type apparatus 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH (6.8) as dissolution medium. The temperature of the dissolution medium was maintained at 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C, an aliquot of dissolution medium was withdrawn at every 5 min interval and filtered. The absorbance of the filtered solution was measured by UV spectrophotometric method at 237.5 nm and concentration of the drug was determined from standard calibration curve [56-58].

STABILITY STUDIES:

Stability testing of optimized formulation batch F4 was carried out to determine the stability of drug and carrier and also to determine the physical stability of formulation under accelerated storage condition. The prepared tablets were placed in borosilicate screw-capped glass containers. The samples were kept at the condition of 45 $^{\circ}$ C/75%RH and were analyzed at 0, 14, 21 and 28 days [59-60].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**PREFORMULATION STUDIES:****FTIR STUDIES:**

Figure: 2 FTIR spectrum of pure drug.

Figure: 3 FTIR Spectrum of drug and HPMC 4M.

Figure: 4 FTIR Spectrum of drug + HPMC 15M.

Figure: 5 FTIR Spectrum of drug + HPMC 100M.

Figure: 6 FTIR Spectrum of drug + sodium CMC.

Figure:7 FTIR Spectrum Drug+Na.CMC+HPMC15M+HPMC4M+HPMC 100M.

The FT-IR spectra of the Metformin HCl, sodium CMC, HPMC 15M, HPMC 4M and HPMC 100M the drug-polymer mixture was recorded to check interaction between drug and polymers. The characteristic peaks of Metformin HCl appeared in all the spectra and values were shifted due to the formation of the complex. Metformin was 3291 cm^{-1} which are due to N-H stretching of the functional group present in all the spectrum. This indicated that there was no chemical interaction between drug and other excipients.

Differential Scanning Colorimetry (DSC) STUDIES:

Figure: 8 PURE DRUG.

Figure: 9 DRUG+HPMC 15M.

Figure: 10 DRUG+HPMC 100M.

Figure: 11 DRUG+HPMC 4M.

While in the drug the melting point of Metformin HCl having the endothermic peak at 235.6⁰ C, which corresponds to its melting point this means that the drug loses the crystalline state and converted to an amorphous form, which indicated the excipients do not change the physical state of drug in the physical mixture and there is no chemical interaction between drug and the excipients.

Precompression studies

Table No. 2 Precompression studies of granules.

F. No.	Angle of Repose(θ)	Bulk Density (g/cm^3)	Tapped density (g/cm^3)	Hausner's ratio (kg/cm^2)	Carr's index
F1	26.46 \pm 0.54	0.49 \pm 0.14	0.57 \pm 0.04	1.14 \pm 0.01	14.84 \pm 0.72
F2	25.16 \pm 0.96	0.51 \pm 0.16	0.56 \pm 0.03	1.17 \pm 0.02	15.03 \pm 0.83
F3	24.01 \pm 0.59	0.48 \pm 0.18	0.62 \pm 0.06	1.16 \pm 0.01	16.19 \pm 0.41
F4	27.12 \pm 0.58	0.49 \pm 0.21	0.60 \pm 0.07	1.19 \pm 0.01	14.74 \pm 0.97
F5	25.11 \pm 0.61	0.50 \pm 0.22	0.54 \pm 0.09	1.14 \pm 0.02	15.48 \pm 0.62
F6	24.16 \pm 0.66	0.51 \pm 0.22	0.51 \pm 0.04	1.17 \pm 0.04	13.31 \pm 0.99
F7	26.04 \pm 0.6	0.52 \pm 0.14	0.62 \pm 0.06	1.16 \pm 0.02	12.67 \pm 0.65
F8	25.03 \pm 0.45	0.47 \pm 0.23	0.58 \pm 0.05	1.14 \pm 0.01	13.73 \pm 0.89
F9	25.36 \pm 0.72	0.48 \pm 0.19	0.41 \pm 0.09	1.18 \pm 0.01	14.57 \pm 0.76
F10	26.32 \pm 0.66	0.42 \pm 0.24	0.56 \pm 0.50	1.19 \pm 0.02	15.64 \pm 0.41
F11	25.12 \pm 0.51	0.41 \pm 0.18	0.57 \pm 0.04	1.17 \pm 0.01	14.12 \pm 0.83
F12	25.20 \pm 0.42	0.45 \pm 0.14	0.59 \pm 0.08	1.15 \pm 0.03	13.28 \pm 0.62

The results of the angle of repose of the powder of the formulas ranged from (24.01 \pm 0.59 to 27.12 \pm 0.58) respectively. The results of loose bulk density and tapped density ranged from (0.41 \pm 0.18 to 0.51 \pm 0.22) and (0.41 \pm 0.09 to 0.62 \pm 0.06), respectively. The results of Hausner's ratio and Carr's index ranged from (1.14 \pm 0.01 to 1.14 \pm 0.01) and (13.28 \pm 0.62 to 16.19 \pm 0.41), respectively. The results of the angle of repose (<30) indicate good flow properties of granules. All experiments were carried out in triplicate (n=3).

Formulation development of Mucoadhesive buccal tablet of the F4 dosage form:

Tablets containing 500mg of Metformin HCl were prepared by direct compression method and the various formulae used in the study are shown in table 5.7. The drug, diluents superdisintegrants were passed in #40. All the above ingredients were properly mixed together (in a poly-bag). Talc and magnesium stearate were passed through sieve # 80 and blended with the initial mixture in a Polybag. The powder blend was compressed into tablets on a ten- station rotary punch – tableting machine (Rimek Mini Press -1) using 7mm concave punch set.

POST-COMPRESSION STUDIES:

Table No. 3 Post compression studies of the formulated tablet.

Formulation No.	Thickness (mm-mean)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Weight Variation (%) mean±SD	Drug content (%)	Friability (%)
F1	3.31±0.01	5.11±0.40	668.7	92.31	0.85
F2	3.30±0.02	4.62±0.49	667.8	90.67	0.83
F3	3.33±0.03	4.01±0.37	668.1	96.42	0.84
F4	3.34±0.02	4.01±0.51	669.7	91.49	0.72
F5	3.32±0.01	4.25±0.37	664.3	94.07	0.65
F6	3.33±0.02	4.30±0.41	662.3	95.16	0.73
F7	2.47±0.04	4.30±0.44	667.1	95.12	0.85
F8	2.43±0.03	4.20±0.40	666.7	93.71	0.65
F9	2.41±0.03	4.24±0.52	668.1	96.14	0.52
F10	3.41±0.02	4.21±0.40	667.2	93.12	0.82
F11	2.43±0.05	4.23±0.36	668.7	94.18	0.73
F12	2.42±0.01	5.03±0.32	667.9	95.21	0.75

The prepared tablets in all the formulations possessed good mechanical strength with significant hardness in the range of 4.01±0.37 to 5.11±0.40 sq. cm. Friability values below 1% were an indication of the good mechanical resistance of the tablets. Formulations prepared by direct compression method were found to be more friable. All the tablets from each formulation passed weight variation was within the pharmacopeia limits of $\pm 7.5\%$ of the weight. The weight variation in all six formulations was found to be 662.3 to 669.7 mg, which was in pharmacopeia limits of $\pm 7.5\%$ of the average weight. The percentage drug content of all the tablets was found to be between 96.42 to 90.67 of Metformin tablets which were within the acceptable limits.

Table No. 4 Post formulation studies of the Mucoadhesive dosage forms.

F.no.	Swelling index	Mucoadhesive strength	Disintegration Time (min)
F1	103.12	18.16	6.15
F2	96.67	16.47	5.44
F3	98.14	17.09	5.32
F4	101.32	16.45	5.02
F5	98.64	15.76	6.14
F6	94.67	15.12	5.09
F7	102.00	15.03	5.56
F8	95.33	14.76	5.32
F9	98.67	13.19	5.18
F10	95.45	12.89	6.02
F11	93.31	12.44	5.28
F12	94.12	13.01	5.14

The results of Swelling index, mucoadhesive strength and *in vitro* disintegrating time (sec) ranged from 103.12 to 93.31, 12.11 to 18.16 and 5.02 to 6.15 min respectively. All the studies are within pharmacopeia limits and pose good accessibility to the formulation developments

IN VITRO PROFILE OF MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLETS OF METFORMIN HCL

Figure:12 *In vitro* dissolution profile of F1 toF3.

Figure 13: *In vitro* dissolution profile of F4 toF6.

Figure:14 *In vitro* dissolution profile of F7 toF9.

Figure 15: *In vitro* dissolution profile of F10 to F12.

The dissolution studies were done for the twelve formulas of prepared Metformin HCl tablet in comparison with the formulas. The *In vitro* dissolution profile indicated faster and maximum drug release from the formulation F4.

***In-vitro* RELEASE KINETICS**

Table No 5: R² value and n result table.

F. code	R ² value				N value
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	
F1	0.916	0.986	0.982	0.966	0.637
F2	0.907	0.976	0.976	0.974	0.723
F3	0.927	0.996	0.985	0.995	0.658
F4	0.947	0.938	0.999	0.998	0.490
F5	0.914	0.987	0.983	0.976	0.698
F6	0.944	0.994	0.995	0.997	0.640
F7	0.935	0.986	0.989	0.966	0.645
F8	0.908	0.992	0.980	0.968	0.667
F9	0.974	0.994	0.987	0.992	0.752
F10	0.916	0.986	0.982	0.966	0.637
F11	0.907	0.976	0.976	0.974	0.723
F12	0.927	0.996	0.985	0.995	0.658

Figure 16: Higuchi plot for F1, F2 and F3 formulations.

Figure 17: Higuchi plot for F4, F5 and F6 formulations.

Figure 18: Higuchi plot for F7, F8 and F9 formulations.

Figure:19 Higuchi plot for F10, F11 and F12 formulations.

Figure 20: Korsmayers pepas plot for F1, F2 and F3 formulation.

Figure 21: Korsmayerspepas plot for F4, F5 and F6 formulations.

Figure 22: Korsmayerspepas plot for F7, F8 and F9 formulations.

Figure 23: Korsmayerspepas plot for F10, F11 and F12 formulations.

Figure 24: First order plot for F1, F2 and F3 formulations.

Figure 25: First order plot for F4, F5 and F6 formulations.

Figure:26 First order plot for F7, F8 and F9 formulations.

Figure 27: First order plot for F10, F11 and F12 formulations.

Among the different control release polymers HPMC 100M (F4) were showing highest drug release retarding capacity. For the F4 formulation diffusion exponent n value is in between 0.45 to 0.89 so they are following non fickian anomalous diffusion model.

ACCELERATED STABILITY STUDIES:**Table No 6: Accelerated Stability studies of the ideal formulation.**

Parameter days	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Drug Content (%)	<i>In-vitro</i> disintegration time (min)	<i>In-vitro</i> drug release study
0	669.1	98.47	5.86	98.8
14	668.2	98.01	6.02	98.1
21	668.9	97.43	6.84	97.6
28	667.2	96.42	7.12	97.4

An optimized batch F4 was carried for stability study to its higher release, lower disintegration time, hardness and drug content. So, accelerated stability studies (AST) was carried for optimized batch F4 exposing it to 45⁰c/75%RH for 0, 14, 21 and 28 days. The sample was analyzed for hardness, drug content *In Vitro* disintegration time and *In- vitro* dissolution studies.

CONCLUSION

As an important pharmaceutical technology, mucoadhesive tablets should be delivered considering numerous factors. However, the lack of consolidated information impairs the process of constructing concrete association between these parameters, being common to consider only the polymer chosen as the main important factor in mucoadhesive tablets development. Among other results, this article demonstrates that this technology depends not only on a detailed analysis of the polymer but also the physical characteristics of the tablet, the physicochemical characteristics of the drug to be incorporated and the buccal region in which it will remain in contact.

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